

Solvent Effect and Mechanism of The Base Hydrolysis of Ethyl Levulinate

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The hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate has been carried out in dioxane-water and acetone-water media at different temperatures under isodielectric conditions. The kinetics followed a mixed order process, via 'a true bimolecular second order' and an 'apparent second order termolecular process'. Amounts of reaction proceeding via each path together with the thermodynamic functions associated with the activation process characterising each mechanism have been evaluated.

THE kinetics of the hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate has been studied in organo-aqueous binaries with a view to an understanding of the role of water in the hydrolysis mechanism. The treatment has been made in a similar manner as in the case of β keto ester.

Experimental

Ethyl levulinate has been prepared by the standard method. Acetone was purified by a standard procedure. Dioxane was made acid free and distilled before use.

The kinetic study involved the method of titration. Two aquo-organic media, (i) dioxane-water and (ii) acetone-water, were used as solvents in the alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate. Different compositions of the solvent mixtures were used in order to maintain isodielectric media as in the previous studies with ethyl pyruvate³ and ethylacetoacetate¹.

Results and Discussion

The rates for the alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate in a series of dioxane-water mixtures with dielectric constants ranging from 12 to that of pure water, measured at different temperatures, indicate an overall second order rate law. A collection of the rate constants is presented in Table 1. The corresponding second order rate constants in acetone-water media are presented in Table 2.

The rate constant data in Table 1 and 2 together with the curve of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/T$ (not shown) enabled the computation of kinetic parameters for the hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate in the media of different dielectric constants.

The technique of variation of the dielectric constant to ascertain the possible role of water in the hydrolytic mechanism has been used, as in the case of ethyl acetoacetate¹ and ethyl pyruvate³. The graphs of $\log k_{obs}$ against the reciprocals of the dielectric constants of dioxane-water media at different temperatures are not linear. The points, as for the ethyl

aceto-acetate system¹, may be housed on two straight lines (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Water-dioxane medium

A—25°C
B—30°C
C—35°C
D—40°C
E—45°C

The distinctive feature, however, is that when k_{obs} is plotted against the concentration of water in the binary medium, a practically linear graph with a definite intercept results (Fig. 3) for each temperature, unlike a pair of two intersecting straight lines as for the β keto ester system¹. Other trial plots of k_{obs} vs $[H_2O]^n$, where n is different from unity, result in nonlinear graphs (not shown). The plots (Fig. 3) lead to two immediate observations.

(i) They are straight lines; (ii) The straight lines make definite intercepts. Each of these two aspects

TABLE 1. BASE HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL LEVULINATE SOLVENT : WATER AND DIOXANE-WATER

Dielectric constant	Temp. °C	k_{obs} (Lit mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	ΔH^* (K. Cal/ gm. mole)	A	ΔS^* (e.u.)	T ΔS^* (K. Cal/ gm. mole)	ΔF^* (K. Cal/ gm. mole)
Pure water	25	8.5					
	30	12.0					
	35	18.0	16.9	$10^{13.2}$	-6.40	-2.0	18.9
	40	23.0					
	45	30.5					
69.0	25	7.25					
	30	10.5					
	35	17.0	15.4	10^{12}	-11.9	-3.7	19.1
	40	21.5					
	45	28.0					
62.5	25	6.39	%				
	30	9.7					
	35	15.75	13.7	$10^{10.8}$	-17.4	-5.4	19.1
	40	20.0					
	45	26.66					
49.5	25	5.75					
	30	8.75					
	35	14.5	12.9	$10^{10.2}$	-20.1	-6.2	19.1
	40	18.0					
	45	25.0					
36.0	25	4.7					
	30	8.0					
	35	13.25	12.3	$10^{9.7}$	-22.5	-6.9	19.2
	40	16.3					
	45	23.0					
12.0	25	3.0					
	30	5.5					
	35	9.0	11.5	$10^{8.9}$	-26.2	-8.1	19.6
	40	11.5					
	45	18.0					

TABLE 2. BASE HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL LEVULINATE SOLVENT : ACETONE-WATER

Dielectric constant	Temp. °C	k_{obs} (Lit mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	ΔH^* (K. Cal/ gm. mole)	A	ΔS^* (e.u.)	T ΔS^* (K. Cal/ gm. mole)	ΔF^* (K. Cal/ gm. mole)
69.5	10	2.31					
	20	4.35					
	25	7.18	15.5	$10^{12.1}$	-11.4	-3.4	18.9
	30	10.0					
	35	17.0					
58.0	10	1.95					
	20	3.66					
	25	6.0	14.3	$10^{11.2}$	-16.5	-4.8	19.1
	30	9.0					
	35	15.7					
45.5	10	1.5					
	20	3.0					
	25	4.83	12.7	10^{10}	-21.0	-6.3	19.0
	30	7.9					
	35	14.1					
31.5	10	1.01					
	20	2.25					
	25	3.5	12.1	$10^{9.5}$	-23.3	-6.8	18.9
	30	6.33					
	35	12.25					

will have its bearing on the mechanism proposed. In keeping with the fact that only one straight line is obtained instead of two in the plot of k_{obs} vs $[H_2O]$ in the dioxane-water binary, it is likely that water participation in the hydrolysis mechanism takes place in such a way as to make the rate determining step either

(a) an apparently second order bimolecular process or

(b) an apparently second order termolecular process, and not a combination of the two, when the whole range of the dielectric constants of the media is considered. Briefly speaking, over the dielectric range investigated, the alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate is a second order bimolecular or a second order termolecular process involving acyl oxygen scission. In (a) the word 'apparent' is used in order to avoid confusion with the true second order bimolecular process. Because here the rate determining step (scheme not shown) apparently depends on the 1st power of ester-hydroxide adduct concentration.

Fig. 2. Water-acetone medium

A—10°C
B—20°C
C—25°C
D—30°C
E—35°C

A preferential choice of one of the two alternatives can not be made outright. But the magnitudes of the entropies of activation and frequency factors (Table 1) can serve as a possible guide. If the comparison of ΔS^* and A values for ethyl levulinate system be made with the corresponding data for ethyl acetoacetate system in dioxane-water binary, these are not widely different in the two cases except perhaps for pure water and dioxane-water system of dielectric constants 69.0 and 62.5.

Considering these aspects of frequency factors and activation entropies as in the case of β keto

system, it may be argued that possibly the scheme *b* rather than *a* is operative in the hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate. We now turn to the second feature of the graphs of k_{obs} vs $[H_2O]$ (Fig. 3). The fact that at each temperature the straight lines make definite intercepts with k_{obs} axis indicates a simultaneous existence of a hydrolysis mechanism wherein water plays no role in the rate determining stage, but must be involved in a step either prior to or subsequent

Fig. 3. Concentration of water in gram moles per litre (Water-dioxane medium).

A—25°C
B—30°C
C—35°C
D—40°C
E—45°C

Fig. 1. Concentration of water in gram moles per litre (Water acetone medium).

A—10°C
B—20°C
C—25°C
D—30°C
E—35°C

to it. In other words, this part of the mechanism can be assumed to be a "pure second order bimolecular acyl oxygen scission mechanism", if the latter is to be elucidated within the framework of a conventionally accepted mechanism⁴⁻⁷. So, it can be concluded that the hydrolysis throughout the whole range of the dielectric constants proceeds by (i) an

apparently second order termolecular mechanism and (ii) true second order bimolecular mechanism.

In acetone-water media, a two-straight-lines accommodation of points in $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ (Fig. 2) and a simple straight line plot of k_{obs} vs $[H_2O]$ (Fig. 4) are similar to the ones described for dioxane-water media. The entropies of activation and the frequency factors are also of similar magnitudes in the two media for ethyl levulinate. The interpretation of the mechanism of hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate in different acetone-water media is, therefore, exactly analogous to the one suggested for dioxane-water media in the foregoing paragraph.

On the basis of the suggested schemes, two tables (Table 3 & 4) are presented showing split rate constants and the percentage of reaction proceeding via each mechanism, both for dioxane-water and acetone-water media.

It may, however, be noted that in most of the general cases⁸⁻¹², plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ is found to be partly linear for the higher dielectric constant ranges, and that the points deviate from the straight

line for lower dielectric constants. This deviation from linearity is partly ascribed by kineticists¹³ to the initiation and operation of a new mechanism. This view seems applicable to the alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl acetoacetate¹ where the points of intersection in the $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ curves represent approximately the same composition of dioxane-water or of acetone-water mixture as do the points of intersection in the curves of k_{obs} vs $[H_2O]$. These points incidentally also represent the termination and initiation of the suggested initial and subsequent mechanisms respectively.

The alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl levulinate, however, shows points of intersection in the $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ curves (vide Fig. 1 and 2), but no break is observed in k_{obs} vs $[H_2O]$ graph (Fig. 3 and 4). So there is no necessity of proposing the initiation of any new mechanisms at any composition of organo-aqueous binaries employed. It seems reasonable to assume that the water content of the solvent medium is the more basic correlation factor than the macro-dielectric constant.

TABLE 3. BASE HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL LEVULINATE (WATER-DIOXANE MEDIA.) VALUES OF THE SPLIT RATE CONSTANTS

Temp.	Dielectric constant	Molar conc. of water	k_1' (Lit (mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹))	k_2 (Lit ² (mole ⁻² min ⁻¹))	$k_2[H_2O] = k_2'$ (Lit. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	Percentage of reaction proceeding via	
						True sec. order Bimolecular path	App. sec. order Termolecular path
25	Pure water	55.50	0.6	0.136	7.55	7.4	92.6
	69.0	49.57	"	"	6.74	8.2	91.8
	62.5	45.73	"	"	6.22	8.8	91.2
	49.5	37.94	"	"	5.16	10.4	89.6
	36.0	29.63	"	"	4.03	12.9	87.1
	12.0	13.85	"	"	1.88	24.2	75.8
30	Pure water	55.50	2.7	0.165	9.16	22.7	77.3
	69.0	51.12	"	"	8.43	24.3	75.7
	62.5	46.98	"	"	7.75	25.8	74.2
	49.5	38.70	"	"	6.38	29.7	70.3
	36.0	30.40	"	"	5.02	34.9	65.1
	12.0	14.37	"	"	2.37	53.3	46.7
35	Pure water	55.50	6.6	0.20	11.10	37.3	62.7
	69.0	51.91	"	"	10.38	38.9	61.1
	62.5	47.49	"	"	9.49	41.0	59.0
	49.5	39.49	"	"	7.89	45.5	54.5
	36.0	30.91	"	"	6.18	51.6	48.4
	12.0	14.63	"	"	2.92	69.3	30.7
40	Pure water	55.50	8.4	0.25	13.88	37.5	62.5
	69.0	52.63	"	"	13.15	38.8	61.2
	62.5	48.50	"	"	12.16	40.7	59.3
	49.5	40.23	"	"	10.06	45.3	54.7
	36.0	31.70	"	"	7.92	51.1	48.9
	12.0	14.88	"	"	3.72	69.0	31.0
45	Pure water	55.50	14.1	0.275	15.26	48.0	52.0
	69.0	53.61	"	"	14.78	48.8	51.2
	62.5	49.50	"	"	13.61	50.9	49.1
	49.5	40.97	"	"	11.27	55.6	44.4
	36.0	31.90	"	"	8.77	61.6	38.4
	12.0	15.12	"	"	4.16	77.2	22.8

TABLE 4 HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL IFFULINATE (ACETONE WATER MEDIUM) VALUES OF THE SPLIT RATE CONSTANTS

Temp °C	Diele const	Molar conc of water	k_1 (Lit mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	k_2 (Lit ² mole ⁻² min ⁻¹)	$k_2[\text{H}_2\text{O}] = k_3$ (Lit mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	Percentage of reaction proceeding via	
						True sec order Bimole path	App sec order Termole path
10	Pure water	55.50	0.6	0.004	2.44	19.7	80.3
	69.5	39.96	"	"	1.76	25.4	74.6
	58.0	29.69	"	"	1.30	31.6	68.4
	45.5	19.42	"	"	0.85	41.4	58.6
	31.5	8.87	"	"	0.39	60.6	39.4
20	Pure water	55.50	1.45	0.0675	3.74	27.9	72.1
	69.5	43.80	"	"	2.95	32.9	67.1
	58.0	32.70	"	"	2.21	39.6	60.4
	45.5	21.62	"	"	1.46	49.8	50.2
	31.5	10.53	"	"	0.71	67.1	32.9
25	Pure water	55.50	2.2	0.11	6.10	26.5	73.5
	69.5	44.86	"	"	4.93	30.8	69.2
	58.0	33.52	"	"	3.68	37.4	62.6
	45.5	22.53	"	"	2.48	47.0	53.0
	31.5	11.08	"	"	1.22	64.3	35.7
30	Pure water	55.50	4.85	0.117	6.49	42.8	57.2
	69.5	46.98	"	"	5.49	46.9	53.1
	58.0	35.27	"	"	4.13	54.0	46.0
	45.5	23.77	"	"	2.78	63.6	36.4
	31.5	11.88	"	"	1.39	77.2	22.8
35	Pure water	55.50	10.5	0.136	7.55	58.2	41.8
	69.5	48.86	"	"	6.64	61.3	38.7
	58.0	37.00	"	"	5.03	67.6	32.4
	45.5	24.58	"	"	3.34	75.9	24.1
	31.5	12.42	"	"	1.69	86.1	13.9

Scatchard¹⁴ pointed out the advisability of using a rate constant value expressed in mole fraction unit rather than in volume concentration unit. The linearity between $\log k$ (mole fraction unit) and the mole fraction of water in the binary solvents observed by Anantakrishnan and Radhakrishnamurti¹⁵ led them to suggest that mole fraction rather than dielectric constant would serve as a better correlation factor. This argument alone does not ensure it to be more fundamental than the dielectric constant in the latter and the mole fractions of water in the solvent mixtures are, as actual plots indicate, linearly related.

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